

Control and paralysis? A context-sensitive analysis of objections to supermajorities in constitutional adjudication

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Supermajorities in judicial review are present in several countries, including the United States (at the state level), Mexico, Peru, the Czech Republic, Chile, and South Korea. Despite their prevalence, the theoretical legitimacy of supermajorities has been a topic of intense debate since the early twenty-first century. A notable gap exists between this theoretical discourse and empirical research that examines the supermajority models in practice. This article endeavors to bridge this gap. Focusing on two important concerns raised in comparative scholarship—namely that supermajorities might enable political branches to control the court through select appointments, and they could potentially paralyze constitutional courts—this article offers a nuanced examination of the Mexican scenario. It argues that specific mechanisms governing judicial appointments, such as staggered terms and pluralistic appointments, can effectively mitigate the risk of court control in supermajority settings. Furthermore, a thorough assessment of an ad hoc dataset on decisions in which the supermajority was applicable suggests that these majorities do not paralyze the court.

1. Introduction: A literature review of supermajorities in constitutional adjudication

Judges decide on the constitutionality of statutes by deliberating and voting. The majority rule (simple majority) is often considered the most common decisional rule in courts. However, supermajorities appeared in both the American and Kelsenian models of judicial review. At the beginning of the twentieth century, several states

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in the United States adopted supermajority rules to strike down legislation (Ohio, North Dakota, and Nebraska). In turn, in the Kelsenian model, the Czechoslovak Constitutional Court in 1920 also functioned under a supermajority.

Discussions on supermajorities may be divided into two different groups. In the first place, design-based studies typically concentrate on the effects of supermajorities within a single jurisdiction. For example, early on, Madgett analyzed the rule in Nebraska;¹ Madox, Hausser, and Stene considered its impact in Ohio;² while Riley later conducted a similar analysis.³ Other scholars from several jurisdictions undertook a similar study in the Dominican Republic,⁴ Mexico,⁵ South Korea,⁶ and Peru,⁷ among others.⁸ This body of literature, mainly empirical in nature, does not contribute much to the philosophical debate on supermajorities and rarely embarks on comparative studies.

A distinct body of literature delves into the theoretical debate surrounding the philosophical justification of supermajorities. At the beginning of the 2000s, insightful analyses published by Shugerman, Caminker, and Gersen and Vermeule elevated the discussion of supermajorities to a theoretical plane.⁹ Even though those contributions primarily centered on the US jurisdiction, they offered nuanced theoretical defenses of supermajorities, igniting a more profound debate. Subsequently, Waldron challenged bare majorities as decisional models.¹⁰ This thought-provoking perspective gained traction in academic circles, leading to subsequent works that either defended (like Guha Krishnamurthi¹¹) or criticized (like Cristóbal Caviedes¹²) the use of simple majorities in constitutional adjudication.

¹ Paul W. Madgett, *The Five-Judge Rule in Nebraska*, 2 CREIGHTON L. REV. 329 (1968).

² W. Rolland Maddox, *Minority Control of Court Decisions in Ohio*, 24 AM. POL. SCI. REV. 638 (1930); Robert L. Hausser, *Limiting the Voting Power of the Supreme Court: Procedure in the States*, 5 OHIO STATE UNIV. LAW J. 54 (1939); Edwin O. Stene, *Is There Minority Control of Court Decisions in Ohio?*, 9 U. CINCINNATI L. REV. 23 (1935).

³ William Jay Riley, *To Require That a Majority of the Supreme Court Determine the Outcome of Any Case Before It*, 50 NEB. L. REV. 622 (1970).

⁴ I EDUARDO JORGE PRATS, DERECHO CONSTITUCIONAL 453 (3d ed. 2015).

⁵ JOAQUÍN BRAGE, LA ACCIÓN ABSTRACTA DE INCONSTITUCIONALIDAD (2005).

⁶ Joon Seok Hong, *Signaling the Turn: The Supermajority Requirement and Judicial Power on the Constitutional Court of Korea*, 67 AM. J. COMP. L. 177 (2019).

⁷ Nestor Sagües, *Los poderes implícitos e inherentes del Tribunal Constitucional del Perú y el quórum para sus votaciones*, in LA CONSTITUCIÓN DE 1993: ANÁLISIS Y COMENTARIOS 3 (Francisco Fernández ed., 1996); Francisco Fernández Segado, *El Control Normativo de La Constitucionalidad En El Perú: Crónica de Un Fracaso Anunciado*, REVISTA ESPAÑOLA DE DERECHO CONSTITUCIONAL 11 (1999). On the courts' ability to strike down legislation in Peru under supermajority rules, see also Eduardo Dargent, *Determinants of Judicial Independence: Lessons from Three "Cases" of Constitutional Courts in Peru (1982–2007)*, 41 J. LATIN AM. STUD. 251 (2009).

⁸ However, with the exception of Hong's analysis (*supra* note 6), no other studies have comparative remarks.

⁹ Jed Handelsman Shugerman, *A Six-Three Rule: Reviving Consensus and Deference on the Supreme Court*, 37 GA. L. REV. 893 (2003); Evan H. Caminker, *Thayerian Deference to Congress and Supreme Court Supermajority Rule: Lessons from the Past*, 78 IND. L.J. 73 (2003); Jacob E. Gersen & Adrian Vermeule, *Chevron as a Voting Rule*, 116 YALE L.J. 676 (2007) (however, not concerned with constitutional adjudication).

¹⁰ Jeremy Waldron, *Five to Four: Why Do Bare Majorities Rule on Courts?*, 123 YALE L.J. 1692 (2014).

¹¹ Guha Krishnamurthi, *For Judicial Majoritarianism*, 22 U. PA. J. CONST. L. 1201 (2019).

¹² Cristóbal Caviedes, *Is Majority Rule Justified in Constitutional Adjudication?*, 41 OXFORD J. LEGAL STUD. 376 (2021).

Consequently, several authors have recently championed supermajorities from a theoretical standpoint. For example, Pablo Castillo-Ortiz proposed to explore supermajority requirements as a feature in new designs of Kelsenian constitutional courts.¹³ Yaniv Roznai posited that a supermajority could serve as a model to ensure judicial deference to political institutions.¹⁴ Meanwhile, Caviedes presented a compelling defense of supermajorities in constitutional courts on Condorcetian accuracy principles to foster consensus and uphold the presumption of constitutionality.¹⁵ These scholars have also emphasized the possible shortcomings of supermajorities, such as the increasing difficulty of striking down unconstitutional legislation,¹⁶ the possible paralysis of the court,¹⁷ or potential for political branches to exert undue influence over the court.¹⁸ Many theories discussed can be empirically tested based on the behavior of supermajorities in systems that operate under them.

In summary, a global discourse on supermajority rule in constitutional adjudication—its design, advantages, and potential problems—is gaining momentum. Yet, gaps remain in the literature. First, there is a need for further empirical research on how constitutional courts function under supermajority rule; our understanding of the courts is limited. Second, existing empirical analyses are either outdated or too localized, often neglecting the broader ongoing debate on supermajorities.

This article aims to bridge one such gap by addressing the objections of court control and court paralysis, as highlighted by international scholars, using the Mexican supermajority as a case study. Simultaneously, the article will enrich the design-based literature by providing empirical insights into the rule's operation in a jurisdiction previously unexplored by comparative research.

The remainder of the article is structured as follows: Section 2 outlines the essential components of the Mexican supermajority. Section 3 tackles the objection that supermajorities might enable political branches to control courts by packing them with a minority of loyal judges (the court control argument). I try to demonstrate that such an objection relies on features external to the supermajority system and can be challenged through contextual analysis. In Section 4, I examine the notion that supermajorities might lead to paralyzing the court (the court paralysis argument). Using statistical data from the Mexican scenario, I will present strong evidence suggesting that supermajorities likely do not impede the court's functioning and might only affect a small proportion of cases. I conclude with the assertion that the Mexican case provides compelling arguments for the viability of supermajorities.

¹³ Pablo Castillo-Ortiz, *The Dilemmas of Constitutional Courts and the Case for a New Design of Kelsenian Institutions*, 39 *LAW & PHIL.* 617 (2020).

¹⁴ Yaniv Roznai, *Introduction: Constitutional Courts in a 100-Years Perspective and a Proposal for a Hybrid Model of Judicial Review*, 14 *VIENNA J. ON INT'L CONST. L.* 355, 366 (2021).

¹⁵ Cristóbal Caviedes, *A Core Case for Supermajority Rules in Constitutional Adjudication*, 20 *INT'L J. CONST. L.* 1162 (2022).

¹⁶ Roznai, *supra* note 14, at 371.

¹⁷ Castillo-Ortiz, *supra* note 13, at 640.

¹⁸ See WOJCIECH SADURSKI, *POLAND'S CONSTITUTIONAL BREAKDOWN* 73 (2019) (arguing that the introduced combination of rules in the Polish case would allow newly appointed loyal judges to veto decisions on the unconstitutionality of statutes).

2. The Mexican supermajority in context

Mexico implemented the supermajority through a 1994 constitutional amendment. However, the change was a reaction to the previous constitutional review system. To understand the present, we must understand the past.

2.1. Mexico's judicial review: From *amparo* to the supermajority

From 1847 to 1994, laws in Mexico could only be challenged through *amparo*, an individual constitutional complaint that allows for judicial review with *inter partes* effect. An *amparo* ruling could only issue an injunction protecting the plaintiff. To everyone else, the statute remained applicable and was still presumed constitutional.¹⁹

In 1994, a radical constitutional amendment vested the Supreme Court with augmented powers, reshaping it into a Constitutional Court characterized by a high level of independence. There are several theories behind the amendment. One theory claims that President Zedillo and the Partido de la Revolución Institucional (PRI), anticipating the mounting influence of the opposition and the potential of election losses,²⁰ sought to institute structures that could effectively resolve political conflicts,²¹ adapting to a democratizing context.²² A second theory was that the dominant party's aim was primarily to create a legitimizing veneer.²³

With its newly acquired powers and autonomy, the Court asserted itself as able and willing to control governmental action and legislation.²⁴ The amendment revitalized a previously overlooked procedure ("constitutional controversies") and reformed it to permit governmental branches to present jurisdictional disputes before the court. Additionally, the possibility to file abstract challenges to legislation—a staple in the Kelsenian model of constitutional review—made its first appearance in Mexico's legal system. Parliamentary minorities (33%) and the Attorney General were granted legal standing to file abstract challenges to legislation without needing to prove legal interest.²⁵ If the suit succeeded, the contested provisions would be expunged from the legal framework. It was the first instance in nearly 150 years since the introduction of *amparo* that the Court could declare a statute unconstitutional not only in a concrete

¹⁹ Mauro Arturo Rivera León, *¿La tumba de Otero? Naturaleza, funcionamiento y problemáticas de la declaratoria general de inconstitucionalidad en México*, 26 ANUARIO IBEROAMERICANO DE JUSTICIA CONSTITUCIONAL 59 (2022).

²⁰ Jodi Finkel, *Judicial Reform as Insurance Policy: Mexico in the 1990s*, 47 LATIN AM. POL. & SOC'Y 87 (2005). See similarly Stephen Zamora & José Ramón Cossío, *Mexican Constitutionalism after Presidencialismo*, 4 INT'L J. CONST. L. 411, 421 (2006).

²¹ Roberto Niembro Ortega, *John Hart Ely in the Mexican Supreme Court*, 19 INT'L J. CONST. L. 533, 537 (2021).

²² Silvia Inclán, *Judicial Reform in Mexico: Political Insurance or the Search for Political Legitimacy?*, 62 POL. RESCH. Q. 753, 762 (2009).

²³ Juan Antonio Mayoral Díaz-Asensio, *¿Por qué los autócratas limitan judicialmente su poder? Un análisis comparado del establecimiento de altos tribunales en regímenes autoritarios*, 2012 REVISTA DE ESTUDIOS POLÍTICOS 41, 64. See also Pilar Domingo, *Judicial independence: the politics of the Supreme Court in Mexico*, 32 J. LATIN AM. STUD. 705, 728 (2000) (arguing that it seemed to represent "a sincere governmental initiative" from the beginning. However, she did not disregard the possibility that it "could be construed as a further example of the resilience and adaptability of an essentially authoritarian regime").

²⁴ Finkel, *supra* note 20, at 799.

²⁵ Abstract normative review in Mexico only allows challenging enacted legislation; and, unlike in France or Chile, preemptive constitutional review of bills is not provided for.

case for a single plaintiff but for the entire country, contingent upon securing a supermajority of eight votes.

2.2. How many justices does it take to strike down a law? An analysis of the Mexican supermajority

Historically, the introduction of the supermajority in Mexico occurred in tandem with *erga omnes* effects via a constitutional amendment. Mexico possesses a constitutional, rather than a statutory, supermajority. Since the Mexican Supreme Court does not admit the “basic structure doctrine,”²⁶ the constitutional supermajority cannot face judicial review scrutiny as happened with statutory supermajorities in Poland,²⁷ Georgia,²⁸ and the United States when the Federal Supreme Court reviewed Ohio’s supermajority.²⁹

Article 105(II) of the Mexican Constitution clearly states that “Supreme Court rulings may only strike down the challenged statutes if approved by at least an eight-vote majority.” Article 107(II) requires a similar supermajority for the general declaration of unconstitutionality.³⁰ Finally, Article 105(I) states that constitutional controversies regarding legal provisions may only have general effects when approved by an eight-vote supermajority.³¹

The Mexican supermajority applies only to specific procedures: actions of unconstitutionality, general declaration of unconstitutionality, and constitutional controversies (all of them belonging to the court’s original jurisdiction). The Mexican Supreme Court consists of eleven justices. The court may issue opinions in Plenary (with eleven justices) or in Chambers (comprising five justices). Only the Plenary is authorized to resolve cases in which the supermajority is applicable.

Both the action of unconstitutionality and the general declaration of unconstitutionality have in common the fact that the supermajority produces *erga omnes* effects in a Kelsenian manner, regardless of the petitioner or legislative body (be it federal or state) that issued the statute.

One of the consequences of the 1994 supermajority was that it created different majorities to strike down legislation. Since the supermajority applied only to specific procedures, a simple majority via *amparo* was sufficient for overturning legislation but

²⁶ For a definition of the basic structure doctrine, see RICHARD ALBERT, CONSTITUTIONAL AMENDMENTS: MAKING, BREAKING, AND CHANGING CONSTITUTIONS 151 (2019).

²⁷ Wyrok Trybunału Konstytucyjnego z dnia 9 marca 2016 r. [TK] [Judgment of the Constitutional Tribunal of Mar. 9, 2016], Sygn. akt K 47/15, DZIENNIK USTAW [Dz. U.] 2018 poz. 1077 (Pol.).

²⁸ Gadaqvevileba sakartvelos sak'onst'it'utsio sasamartl [Decision of the Constitutional Court of Georgia of December 26, 2016], N3/5/768,769,790,792, www.constcourt.ge/ka/judicial-acts?legal=1141 (Georgia).

²⁹ *Ohio v. Akron Park District*, 281 U.S. 74 (1930). For a classic commentary, see Hausser, *supra* note 2, at 73.

³⁰ Constitución Política de los Estados Unidos Mexicanos [CP], art. 107, DIARIO OFICIAL DE LA FEDERACIÓN [DOF] 05-02-1917 (Mex.). A general declaration of unconstitutionality is a procedure that allows the Supreme Court to strike down a provision with *erga omnes* effects provided a supermajority of eight votes is reached. This is an *ex officio* procedure initiated once binding case law is established through *amparo*, where effects are *inter partes*. Essentially, it serves as a bridge between *inter partes* and *erga omnes* effects.

³¹ CP, art. 105 (Mex.).

was limited to *inter partes* effects. The Supreme Court would be unable to strike down a statute in an action of unconstitutionality even if seven justices voted to do so but could consider the same statute unconstitutional through a bare 6-to-5 majority in an *amparo* case. The sole distinction lies in the ruling's implications: universal in the former scenario and limited to the plaintiff in the latter.³² It is only through procedures requiring a supermajority that the Supreme Court can invalidate a statute *erga omnes*.

The option to challenge a statute through *amparo* introduces its own set of complexities. In actions of unconstitutionality, the analysis is abstract. However, in *amparo*, the plaintiff must prove legal interest and the alleged harm. Thus, not all arguments are necessarily eligible for reevaluation in *amparo*. Some arguments, though easily imagined in the abstract but seldom emergent in concrete cases, might already have exhausted their opportunity for assessment if the supermajority fails. Nonetheless, the Mexican supermajority does facilitate further litigation in individual cases.

a) *The required levels of deference and consensus*

The supermajority is applied only to strike down statutes, not to uphold them. A decision to uphold a statute may be made through a simple majority.³³

The Mexican supermajority is what I term a “deferential supermajority.” Deferential supermajorities favor legislation by establishing two decision thresholds: a simple majority to uphold legislation and a supermajority to declare it unconstitutional. These supermajorities enforce a degree of deference toward legislation enacted by a democratically elected branch.

Deferential supermajorities differ radically from what I refer to as “decisional supermajorities,” which necessitate a supermajority to decide a case, regardless of the outcome. For example, a supermajority is needed for the Dominican Constitutional Court to issue a decision, as per Article 186 of the Constitution.³⁴ Upholding a statute or striking it down requires a supermajority. Scholars have often argued that this feature strives for consensus and legitimacy building within the Court.³⁵ Such a design and its objectives differ from the goals of deferential supermajorities.

President Zedillo's proposed constitutional amendment suggested adopting a nine-vote supermajority.³⁶ However, during the legislative debate, Congress reduced it to an eight-vote supermajority. Neither the initial proposal nor the ensuing debate provide comprehensive reasoning for specifically favoring eight or nine votes. Since eight votes

³² The Chilean Constitution adopted a similar system in 2005. A simple majority suffices for decisions regarding concrete review (*inaplicabilidad*) with *inter partes* effects (Article 93.6), while a supermajority is required for *erga omnes* effects (Article 93.7) provided said statute was found unconstitutional during concrete review. CONSTITUCIÓN POLÍTICA DE LA REPÚBLICA DE CHILE [C.P.] art. 93.

³³ This feature thus stands in contrast to procedures under a simple majority, such as *amparo*. In *amparo*, the Court only needs to reach a simple majority to either uphold a statute or consider it unconstitutional, although the latter would result in *inter partes* effects.

³⁴ DOM. REP. CONST. 1844.

³⁵ JORGE PRATS, *supra* note 4, at 453.

³⁶ Jorge Carpizo, *Reformas constitucionales al Poder Judicial Federal y a la jurisdicción constitucional*, 1995 BOLETÍN MEXICANO DE DERECHO COMPARADO 807, 834.

are required, neither a bare majority of 6-to-5 (54%) nor a robust majority of 7-to-4 (63%) is sufficient to strike down legislation using the relevant procedures. At first, the supermajority might appear high, and adopting a 7-to-4 supermajority could have lowered the threshold while still providing deference to Congress.³⁷ Yet, as empirical analysis will later demonstrate, the supermajority is not high enough to paralyze the court (see Section 4). Since the Supreme Court allows plurality opinions, justices need to agree only on the statute's unconstitutionality, not on the reasoning behind it. If eight votes are achieved, differing arguments among them are irrelevant.

The eight-vote requirement (irrespective of the number of justices attending the session) may generate some problems.³⁸ In procedures under the supermajority rule, article 4 of the Organic Law of the Federal Judiciary requires an eight-justice quorum. If ten justices are present, 80% of the Court must agree; if nine, then 88% agreement is required; and unanimity is necessary if only eight justices are present. It is harder to achieve an 8/8 vote than an 8/11 vote. This issue is not unique to Mexico; other jurisdictions with supermajorities, such as South Korea³⁹ and previously Ohio,⁴⁰ have encountered similar challenges. The Mexican Supreme Court does not have alternate justices, and no pool of “substitute judges” is available to replace a justice who cannot attend a session, further complicating the situation.⁴¹

However, the issue of absentee justices in Mexico should not be exaggerated. The Mexican Supreme Court does not hold oral hearings and relies on written submissions. While this practice has its shortcomings, it grants the Court flexibility. The Court has the autonomy to adjust its schedule, postponing a case until an absent justice returns from sick leave or an official assignment. The Czech Constitutional Court, which also functions under a supermajority, adopted similar practices.⁴²

In the Mexican context, temporary absences have a lesser impact on the Court's proceedings. Since the 2020 pandemic, the Court has permitted virtual hearings and

³⁷ *Id.* at 834.

³⁸ BRAGE, *supra* note 5, at 347.

³⁹ Kim Jongcheol, *Some Problems with the Korean Constitutional Adjudication System*, 1 J. KOREAN L. 17, 26–7 (2001).

⁴⁰ In Ohio, it was not initially clear whether absences of justices would constitute a problem. See OHIO CONST., art. IV, § 2 (repealed 1968): “No law shall be held unconstitutional and void by the supreme court without the concurrence of at least all but one of the judges except in the affirmation of the judgment of the Court of Appeals declaring the law unconstitutional and void.” It was unclear whether the majority was to be calculated based on all members of the Court or only those sitting in the case. The Court preferred the former interpretation. See Jonathan L. Entin, *Judicial Supermajorities and the Validity of Statutes: How Mapp Became a Fourth Amendment Landmark Instead of a First Amendment Footnote*, 50 CASE WEST. L. REV. 441, 458, 461 (2002). As Entin demonstrates, “the lack of a full bench could prevent the supreme court from invalidating an unconstitutional law” (*id.* at 461). In 1943, the Ohio Judicial Council recommended adopting a system of alternate justices to solve this issue.

⁴¹ This system appears to be adopted by El Salvador, which operates under a supermajority. El Salvador requires a 4/5 decisional supermajority in its Constitutional Chamber in specific procedures. LEY ORGÁNICA JUDICIAL [LOJ], art. 14, 1994 (El Sal.). Even though alternate justices might address some issues, they can also introduce others, as Jongcheol points out in relation to the Korean supermajority. Jongcheol, *supra* note 40, at 27.

⁴² David Kosař & Ladislav Vyhnaněk, *The Constitutional Court of Czechia*, in 3 THE MAX PLANCK HANDBOOKS IN EUROPEAN PUBLIC LAW. CONSTITUTIONAL ADJUDICATION: INSTITUTIONS 119, 156 (Armin von Bogdandy, Peter Huber, & Christoph Grabenwarter eds., 2020).

deliberations. Although the Court returned to deliberations *in situ* in 2022, it seems to have retained a practice that allows justices to participate remotely,⁴³ making temporary absences less problematic under standard conditions.

However, problems may arise during significant delays in filling a court vacancy. For instance, the Czech Constitutional Court has experienced frequent appointment delays. In 2003, the Court was briefly unable to handle abstract challenges due to justice absences.⁴⁴ Although rare, delays in Mexico have ranged from fifty to 105 days.⁴⁵ The 2004 appointment delays indeed complicated the Court's proceedings, even with adjustment mechanisms in place.

A president might be tempted to delay nominating a justice if his or her policies face judicial scrutiny, especially if the vote is expected to be close. This would force the Court to postpone hearing a case for an extended period, while waiting for new appointments. In the controversial Federal Remuneration Act case,⁴⁶ the vote of Justice González Alcántara (nominated by President López Obrador) was pivotal in striking down the statute. Had the President delayed this nomination, the statute might have not been declared unconstitutional.⁴⁷

In South Korea, some strategic delays related to supermajority requirements appear to have taken place.⁴⁸ The South Korean situation can serve as an example of the potential for presidents to use appointment delays as a tactic to uphold unconstitutional policies. While such strategic nomination delays have yet to occur in Mexico, as opposed to South Korea, the absence of such an event does not discount its future possibility.

The requisite of eight votes also plays a role when the court must rule on recusals, which are rare in actions of unconstitutionality (*acciones de inconstitucionalidad*). Nonetheless, there have been instances where this issue arose. For example, in 2020, a new Organic Law of the Federal Judiciary was passed. Among other changes, the

⁴³ Temporary absences, which might have been a concern in 2005, lost significance given the new remote possibilities. See, e.g., *Acción de inconstitucionalidad 171/2022*, Pleno de la Suprema Corte de Justicia de la Nación [SCJN] [Supreme Court], Feb. 21, 2022 (Mex.) (with Justice Ortiz participating remotely); *Controversia Constitucional 44/2021*, Pleno de la Suprema Corte de Justicia de la Nación [SCJN] [Supreme Court], Apr. 18, 2022 (Mex.) (with Justice Ríos absent during the session, but participating in the deliberation and voting via Zoom).

⁴⁴ Zdeněk Kühn & Jan Kysela, *Nomination of Constitutional Justices in Post-Communist Countries: Trial, Error, Conflict in the Czech Republic*, 2 EUR. CONST. L. REV. 183, 198 (2006).

⁴⁵ César Astudillo, *Artículo 96. Comentario*, in 10 DERECHOS DEL PUEBLO MEXICANO: MÉXICO A TRAVÉS DE SUS CONSTITUCIONES 20, 40 (Cámara de Diputados ed., 2016).

⁴⁶ *Acción de inconstitucionalidad 105/2018 y su acumulada 108/2018*, Pleno de la Suprema Corte de Justicia de la Nación [SCJN] [Supreme Court], May 20, 2019 (Mex.).

⁴⁷ The issue also arose in Korea. Delays in nominations by former President Lee Myung-bak in 2013 resulted in a problematic lack of a full bench to create a supermajority. Hong, *supra* note 6, at 201.

⁴⁸ See *id.* at 66–7. Hong noted an analogous issue in South Korea, albeit not pertaining to a deferential supermajority but rather a six-vote supermajority required to confirm a presidential impeachment. During the impeachment of Park Geun-hye, two justices (Chief Justice Park Han-chul and Justice Lee Jung-mi) were finishing their terms. Amid this backdrop, “there were concerns that Park Geun-hye’s lawyers were attempting to delay the Court proceedings. . . to make it more difficult for the Court to get the necessary six votes to confirm impeachment” (*Id.* at 202). By delaying the procedure, the Court would need to achieve a 6/7 supermajority, notoriously harder than the natural 6/9 supermajority. See further Jin Wook Kim, *Korean Constitutional Court and Constitutionalism in Political Dynamics: Focusing on Presidential Impeachment*, 4 CONST. REV. 222, 239–41 (2018).

reform extended the presidency of the sitting chief justice. This led to a contentious debate: should Chief Justice Zaldívar recuse himself, given that the new law granted him an extended tenure? Some politicians, perhaps not fully grasping the implications of the supermajority, advised the Chief Justice to abstain from the case. Yet, a recusal from Zaldívar would effectively amount to a vote in favor of preserving the statute, thereby complicating the Court's task of achieving the supermajority—shifting the requirement to an 8/10 vote instead of an 8/11. In the end, Chief Justice Zaldívar did not recuse himself, and the Court went on to unanimously strike down the statute, with Zaldívar's favorable vote.⁴⁹

b) Effects of supermajority failure decisions

In systems where a supermajority is required to strike down legislation, there may be instances where a majority of the court considers a statute unconstitutional, yet the needed supermajority is not achieved. I term these outcomes “supermajority failure decisions.”

In the event of such failures, some constitutional courts produce an opinion that supports the existing legislation. This has been the case in Peru,⁵⁰ the Czech Republic,⁵¹ and South Korea.⁵² Often in these scenarios, the minority, though they carry the court's decision, will pen the majority opinion,⁵³ whereas the court's actual majority (which failed to reach a supermajority) may craft a dissenting opinion. What sets the Mexican system apart is its refusal to automatically uphold the statute when the requisite supermajority is not attained.

The Mexican Constitution does not dwell on the consequences of failing to attain the supermajority. Yet, this is elucidated in a regulatory statute, which stipulates that, in the absence of a supermajority, “the Court shall dismiss the lawsuit and order the case to be closed.”⁵⁴ The word chosen by the lawmakers was “desestimar” (“to dismiss”) rather than “determinar infundado” (“to find groundless,” which would imply upholding the law).

⁴⁹ Acción de inconstitucionalidad 95/2021 y su acumulada, Pleno de la Suprema Corte de Justicia de la Nación [SCJN] [Supreme Court], Nov. 16, 2021 (Mex.).

⁵⁰ This feature stems from a statute in Peru. See *Ley Orgánica del Tribunal Constitucional (LOTIC)*, art. 5 (2004) (providing that: “If the Court fails to reach the qualified five-vote majority, the Court shall issue an opinion declaring the action of unconstitutionality groundless [declarando infundada la demanda]”).

⁵¹ Kosař & Vyhnaněk, *supra* note 43, at 156. See Nález Ústavního soudu ze dne 17. 5. 1994 (ÚS) [Decision of the Constitutional Court of May 17, 1994], Pl. ÚS 36/93, publ. in: Šbírka nálezů a usnesení ÚS, N 24/1 SbNU 175 (Czech.).

⁵² This is a standard practice of the Korean Constitutional Court (KCC). See, e.g., *Unbeobjaepanso* [Const. Ct.], July 29, 2010, 2008 Hun-Ka 19, 2008 Hun-Ba 108, 2009 Hun-Ma 269, 2010 Hun-Ba 38 & 2010 Hun-Ma 275 (consol.) (22-2(A) KCCR 37) (S. Kor.).

⁵³ It might sound paradoxical to refer to the minority opinion that triumphs, given the supermajority, as a “majority opinion.” The KCC avoided this terminology by coining an expression: the “denial opinion.” See *Unbeobjaepanso* [Const. Ct.], May 25, 2006, 2005 Hun-Ma 11 & 2006 Hun-Ma 314 (consol.) (18-1(B) KCCR 134) (S. Kor.). The Mexican case has employed the expression “voto de mayoría no calificada” (non-supermajority opinion).

⁵⁴ *Ley Reglamentaria de las Fracciones I y II del artículo 105 de la Constitución Política de los Estados Unidos Mexicanos* [Regulatory Law of Sections I and II of Article 105 of the Mexican Constitution], *Diario Oficial de la Federación* [DOF] 11-05-1995 (Mex.).

Given that actions of unconstitutionality solely concern constitutional challenges, three potential outcomes exist under the supermajority stipulation: (i) upholding the statute (which requires only a simple majority); (ii) striking down the statute (which requires a supermajority); or (iii) dismissing the case when a majority of the Court believes the statute to be unconstitutional but fails to attain a supermajority. The act of “dismissing” is interpreted by the Court as a formal pronouncement with no precedential value. Dismissals are rulings that neither uphold nor strike down the statute; in other words, the Court decides not to decide. The ruling will lack any written factual or legal reasoning. This mirrors Nebraska’s Supreme Court’s approach in cases of failed supermajority, leaving room for further litigation.⁵⁵

When a “desestimación” occurs, the statute remains in effect, retaining its presumption of constitutionality. Nonetheless, such a statute can still undergo review in *amparo* proceedings,⁵⁶ where only a simple majority is required in multimember judicial bodies, such as circuit courts of appeals, circuit courts, or even the Supreme Court. A supermajority failure does not preclude a further discussion of constitutionality. Specific individuals can seek remedy if they consider their rights violated. A battle not won in the realm of supermajorities may continue in the realm of simple majorities. This feature, albeit with variations, is also evident in Nebraska’s supermajority system.⁵⁷ However, even though subsequent litigation is possible, due to the inherent nature of *amparo*, the debates will be centered on individual cases proving concrete harm. Given the “*inter partes*” rule, *amparo* rulings are also much less disruptive to governmental policy than an action of unconstitutionality.

Mexican scholarship has been mostly critical toward the rule. Since Brage’s critique of the supermajority in 2005,⁵⁸ many have echoed his assessment.⁵⁹

c) Instances of strategic behavior

There is extensive literature on strategic accounts of judicial behavior.⁶⁰ Strategic behavior is not unheard of, even in simple majorities. However, arguably, the unique

⁵⁵ See *Thompson v. Heineman*, 857 N.W.2d 731, 740 (2015). Nonetheless, the Mexican system diverges considerably. In Mexico, the dismissal denotes that no verdict is rendered, whereas in Nebraska the Court did determination on the matter (overturning the district court’s judgment).

⁵⁶ See *Ley de Amparo, Reglamentaria de los artículos 103 y 107 de la Constitución Política de los Estados Unidos Mexicanos [Amparo Act]*, art. 61, *Diario Oficial de la Federación [DO]*, 17-06-2016 (regulating in detail cases in which *amparo* is inadmissible based on formal reasons. The statute does not preclude further litigation if a supermajority is not reached at the Supreme Court in abstract cases).

⁵⁷ See Sandra Zellmer & Kathleen Miller, *The Fallacy of Judicial Supermajority Clauses in State Constitutions*, 47 *U. TOLEDO L. REV.* 73, 86 (2015).

⁵⁸ BRAGE, *supra* note 5, at 341. Brage’s criticism must be taken with a grain of salt, since he did not analyze the rule’s functioning but merely the design of provisions.

⁵⁹ HÉCTOR FIX-ZAMUDIO, *INTRODUCCIÓN AL ESTUDIO DE LA DEFENSA DE LA CONSTITUCIÓN EN EL ORDENAMIENTO MEXICANO* 82–4 (1998); Jorge Carpizo, *Propuestas de modificaciones constitucionales en el marco de la denominada reforma del Estado*, in *EL PROCESO CONSTITUYENTE MEXICANO* 807, 834 (Diego Valadés & Miguel Carbonell eds., 2007); EDUARDO FERRER MAC-GREGOR & RUBÉN SÁNCHEZ, *EFFECTOS Y CONTENIDOS DE LAS SENTENCIAS EN ACCIÓN DE INCONSTITUCIONALIDAD* 19 (2009).

⁶⁰ For classic studies, see LEE EPSTEIN & JACK KNIGHT, *THE CHOICES JUSTICES MAKE* (1997); Lee Epstein & Jack Knight, *Reconsidering Judicial Preferences*, 16 *ANN. REV. POL. SCI.* 11 (2013).

institutional design of supermajority rules might present specific opportunities for distinct behavior. Within the Mexican supermajority framework, two issues stand out, hinting at potential strategic behavior: insincere voting and vote counting.

Although judges might be sincerely open to changing their views and inclined toward consensus, there are instances where judges might sidestep the rule and vote for outcomes they do not sincerely believe in. In South Korea, Hong observed instances where justices may have bargained to prevent a supermajority failure.⁶¹ A comprehensive examination of insincere voting and strategic behavior on the Mexican Supreme Court is beyond the scope of this article.⁶² Even then, such a study might highlight only a few instances where justices voted contrary to their publicly admitted beliefs.⁶³

While uncommon, there are a few documented instances of overt insincere voting. For instance, in cases such as action of unconstitutionality (AI) 15/2018 or Amparo Directo en Revisión 1762/2018, a Justice who initially argued to uphold a provision might change their vote if the supermajority narrowly failed and the counterargument was equally compelling.⁶⁴ In AI 15/2018, after persuasion from Chief Justice Zaldívar, Justice Pardo agreed to vote against a statute, despite personally deeming it constitutional. He even announced he would continue to uphold similar statutes in the future.⁶⁵ In essence, Justice Pardo was not swayed by the arguments of his peers, but felt the supermajority rule might lead to an undesired outcome.

Vote counting, primary overseen by the chief justice, is a distinct matter. A case in point is AI 64/2021.⁶⁶ The Federal Industry Act, backed by MORENA's (the ruling party Movimiento de Regeneración Nacional) parliamentary majority and the president himself, faced opposition from a parliamentary minority. They argued the law contravened the right to a clean environment and unfairly favored state-owned companies over private companies, thus violating constitutional principles of a

⁶¹ Hong, *supra* note 6, at 194–5.

⁶² See Evan H. Caminker, *Sincere and Strategic Voting Norms on Multimember Courts*, 97 MICH. LAW REV. 2297 (1998) (offering a good overview of the concepts, as well as an insightful examination of supermajority coalitions in multimember judicial bodies which is fully applicable to the Mexican case).

⁶³ Court transcripts do not reveal whether justices, in considering the supermajority, might publicly advocate constitutional theories they do not fully endorse in order to strike down a provision.

⁶⁴ See *Acción de Inconstitucionalidad 15/2015*, Pleno de la Suprema Corte de Justicia de la Nación [SCJN] [Supreme Court], Mar. 17, 2016 (Mex.); *Amparo Directo en Revisión 1762/2018*, Pleno de la Suprema Corte de Justicia de la Nación [SCJN] [Supreme Court], Aug. 08, 2018 (Mex.). Even though the supermajority was not applicable in *Amparo Directo en Revisión 1762/2018*, Chief Justice Zaldívar referred to it during the deliberations: “[M]y experience in nine and a half years on the Supreme Court in Plenary is that votes may be changed. For instance, sometimes a vote was undertaken, the result is proclaimed, one vote is missing for the supermajority, and a Justice kindly says: ‘I will change my vote to allow the Court to reach the supermajority.’”

⁶⁵ See *Acción de inconstitucionalidad 15/2018*, Pleno de la Suprema Corte de Justicia de la Nación [SCJN] [Supreme Court], Oct. 08, 2019 (Mex.). (Pardo, J.) (“I have argued why I deem we should not strike down this legal provision. . . . I have no objection to changing my vote to strike it down (given the very peculiar circumstances we face). However, I want to clarify that I will keep on defending the same criteria in further cases, when said situation returns to normality”). See also Caminker, *supra* note 63, at 2322 (pointing out that while forming supermajority coalitions judges would weigh “the institutional values to be gained against the cost of insincerity in the particular case”).

⁶⁶ *Acción de Inconstitucionalidad 64/2021*, Pleno de la Suprema Corte de Justicia de la Nación [SCJN] [Supreme Court], Apr. 07, 2022 (Mex.).

free and competitive market. During deliberations, a supermajority of eight justices claimed the statute was unconstitutional, albeit for varied reasons. Mexico's Supreme Court traditionally employs outcome voting,⁶⁷ where justices must agree on the constitutionality of a law, irrespective of their reasoning. The chief justice, perceived to align ideologically with the ruling party, appeared to shift to issue voting to preserve the statute. Although the chief justice did ask individual justices how their vote should be counted,⁶⁸ the outcome was widely perceived as resulting from an illegitimate maneuver.⁶⁹ Even if some elements of the case remain controversial, it was the chief justice's responsibility to note that the eight-vote threshold had been met, rendering the statute void.

It is worth noting that the most prominent recent examples of supermajority-related strategic behavior involved Chief Justice Zaldívar. Future studies might explore whether supermajorities, given their intricate voting mechanisms, offer chief justices (very often tasked with vote counting and moderating the deliberations) added leverage to advance policy preferences.⁷⁰

In the following sections, I will address in detail two objections that have been raised in the comparative debate on supermajorities. My selection is based on their relevance and the need to empirically validate such hypotheses.⁷¹ I will first address the argument that supermajorities enable political branches to dominate the court by packing it with a few loyal justices. Second, I will empirically examine the notion that the supermajority has paralyzed the court.

3. The court's control argument

3.1. An introduction to the court's control argument

In the global discourse, several scholars have pointed out that supermajorities, combined with appointment mechanisms, might allow politicians to manipulate the court. They could achieve this by fostering a loyal minority of judges capable of

⁶⁷ On the distinction between outcome-voting and issue-voting, see David Post & Steven C. Salop, *Rowing Against the Tide: A Theory of Voting by Multijudge Panels*, 80 *Geo. L.J.* 743 (1991). See also Wolfgang Ernst, *The Fine Mechanisms of Judicial Majoritarianism*, in *COLLECTIVE JUDGING IN COMPARATIVE PERSPECTIVE: COUNTING VOTES AND WEIGHING OPINIONS* 14 (Birke Häcker & Wolfgang Ernst eds., 2020) (preferring the terminology of integral versus sequential voting).

⁶⁸ Roberto Niembro Ortega, *Seeing the Whole Picture of the Debate in the Mexican Supreme Court: A Response to "When Judges Threaten Constitutional Governance: Evidence from Mexico,"* I•CONNECT BLOG (June 29, 2022), <http://www.iconnectblog.com/seeing-the-whole-picture-of-the-debate-in-the-mexican-supreme-court-a-response-to-when-judges-threaten-constitutional-governance-evidence-from-mexico/>

⁶⁹ Mariana Velasco-Rivera, *When Judges Threaten Constitutional Governance: Evidence from Mexico*, I•CONNECT BLOG (June 16, 2022), www.iconnectblog.com/when-judges-threaten-constitutional-governance-evidence-from-mexico/

⁷⁰ There exists a growing comparative literature on the powers of chief justices and how ostensibly administrative functions provide court presidents with significant power to influence the court's direction. For a recent example, see Adam Blisa & David Kosař, *Court Presidents: The Missing Piece in the Puzzle of Judicial Governance*, 19 *GER. L.J.* 2031 (2018).

⁷¹ See similarly Caviedes, *supra* note 15, at 1187.

vetoing decisions on the unconstitutionality of statutes. This possibility was suggested by Sadurski (in the Polish context),⁷² Roznai,⁷³ Dixon and Landau,⁷⁴ and Castillo Ortiz.⁷⁵ I have termed this perspective the “court’s control” argument.

Drawing on this body of literature, I identify the core case of the argument as follows: “A supermajority to strike down legislation allows political power to control the Court by making enough judicial appointments of loyal Justices who insincerely will always vote to defend legislation preventing the supermajority from being reached and allowing the Court to be controlled.”⁷⁶

The court’s control argument is based on insincere voting driven by political motivation. The argument does not object to judges—appointed via robust procedures—voting in favor of preserving a statute, if they have a valid legal rationale for doing so. The harmful aspect is when justices remain beholden to the political entities that appointed them, staunchly defending their statutes and policies irrespective of constitutional challenges, merits of the case, or their personal legal opinion.

To analyze this argument, I will contextualize it within Mexican political dynamics. In the Mexican scenario, the court’s control argument would suggest that the supermajority allows political forces to control the court by installing four loyal justices. Transcending a mere theoretical transposition of international critiques, this criticism genuinely resonates in Mexico. This is accentuated by President López Obrador’s appointment of four out of eleven members of the Supreme Court. Theoretically, these appointments are enough to stymie the Court. Salazar opined that the supermajority culminates in an “absurd” situation: “Arguments and reasoning do not matter. Only votes matter. Therefore, whoever controls four controls everything.”⁷⁷ Salazar’s contention implicitly hints at judicial control. The problem he underscores is not about four justices genuinely disagreeing about a statute’s constitutionality but the potential of them being manipulated. To echo Salazar again: “Whoever *controls* four controls everything.” But is this truly the case?

3.2. A context-sensitive reply: Judicial tenures, pluralism, and constitutional politics against the court’s control argument

The court’s control argument posits that the supermajority enables political control. This assertion presupposes that democratic procedures and checks and balances permit the political majority to appoint (in the Mexican case) four extremely loyal justices. These justices would presumably deviate from established precedents, constitutional texts, and common sense to defend the status quo. Underlying this argument is the idea that a heavily politicized and non-pluralistic

⁷² SADURSKI, *supra* note 18, at 81 (considering the supermajority usage in the Polish case).

⁷³ Roznai, *supra* note 14, at 371.

⁷⁴ See ROSALIND DIXON & DAVID LANDAU, ABUSIVE CONSTITUTIONAL BORROWING: LEGAL GLOBALIZATION AND THE SUBVERSION OF LIBERAL DEMOCRACY 93 (2021).

⁷⁵ Castillo-Ortiz, *supra* note 13, at 640.

⁷⁶ Roznai, *supra* note 14, at 371 (also mentioning this concept as a possible objection. The core case formulation is my own).

⁷⁷ Pedro Salazar, *Cuatro votos judiciales*, HECHOS Y DERECHOS (Feb. 4, 2022), <https://revistas.juridicas.unam.mx/index.php/hechos-y-derechos/article/view/16642/17256>.

appointment procedure would result in justices entirely beholden to political authority and motivated by allegiance rather than legal principles. If supermajority critics hinge their argument on these premises, the argument lacks robustness. If a constitutional system allows a political entity, within a six-year presidential term, to appoint four staunchly loyal justices (the total of appointments that on average a president possesses), who will defend governmental policies without anchoring their decisions in valid legal reasoning, then the supermajority concern is relatively trifling.

After MORENA's 2018 landslide victory, an intriguing temporal coincidence combined with two unusual occurrences allowed President López Obrador to appoint four justices to the Supreme Court within his first three years in office. Although President Peña could have initiated an appointment procedure at the end of his term to replace Justice Cossío, in contrast to his predecessors,⁷⁸ he consciously avoided doing so out of political decorum, calculation, or an undisclosed agreement. A secondary twist was the resignation of Justice Medina Mora in 2019 amidst swirling controversies and conjectures of corruption or political coercion. Both episodes empowered President López Obrador to appoint not two, as he would have otherwise, but four justices during his term.

In terms of nominations, López Obrador's record does not differ from that of his predecessors. President Fox sanctioned four appointments; President Calderón secured five; and President Peña endorsed a more conservative three. The quartet of nominations under López Obrador is par for the course, even factoring in the anomalies. Furthermore, President López Obrador's term ends on September 30, 2024. He will have no further appointments, as Justices Aguilar and Zaldívar will conclude their tenures in December 2024.⁷⁹ The current president did not appoint more justices than usual. Had Medina Mora not resigned and President Peña not given up his nomination, López Obrador would have had the distinction of appointing the fewest justices in modern history. Yet, owing to the above-described events, his nominations were accelerated and clustered within the first half of his presidency.

The political polarization of Mexico also impacted the judiciary. During the political campaign, MORENA employed strong rhetoric painting judges as insensitive to people's needs and as privileged elites perpetuating judicial impunity. In contrast, the opposition criticized every judicial appointment made under MORENA. This heightened polarization heavily affects the Court, which faces an impossible task:

⁷⁸ CÉSAR ASTUDILLO & JOSÉ ESTRADA, NOMBRAMIENTO DE MINISTROS DE LA SUPREMA CORTE DE JUSTICIA DE LA NACIÓN EN EL CONTEXTO DE LOS MODELOS DE DESIGNACIÓN EN EL DERECHO COMPARADO 265 (2019). A debate had arisen as to whether presidents at the end of their term have "diminished constitutional powers" concerning justices' appointments. However, Astudillo contends that appointing a justice at the end of a presidential term would mean that "the possible traces of loyalty or gratitude from the newcomer Justice would dilute rapidly, favoring independence" in light of emerging parliamentary majorities. Astudillo, *supra* note 46, at 44.

⁷⁹ Susana Berruecos García Travesí & Laurence Whitehead, *Constitutional Controversies in the Subnational Democratization of Mexico, 1994–2021*, 12 *LATIN AM. POL'Y* 405, 410 (2021).

it is perceived as a pawn allegedly catering to both governmental and oppositional interests, regardless of its decisions and their underlying reasoning.⁸⁰

The flawed presumptions of the court's control argument are refuted by both legal provisions and political practice. Supreme Court justices enjoy several safeguards against political manipulation. Article 96 of the Constitution establishes a joint procedure, whereby the president, upon a vacancy, proposes three candidates to the Senate. The Senate then must appoint a justice with a two-thirds supermajority. Justices are entitled to a fifteen-year tenure, which guarantees that any justice will outlast at least two presidencies,⁸¹ with the stipulation that non-renewable terms further safeguard justices from political allurements for reappointment.

Historically, the staggered fifteen-year tenures make it challenging for a president to time appointments effectively or attain the essential senatorial supermajorities. For example, President Fox's term, from December 1, 2000 to November 30, 2006, saw him nominate Justices Cossío (in 2003), Luna (early 2004), and Valls (2004). Even though he also proposed Justice Franco (in 2006), the latter began his term only under President Calderón. Thus, practically speaking, Fox appointed only three justices during his administration.

President Calderón, in office from December 1, 2006 to November 30, 2012, made his first appointments rather late, at the end of December 2009. Notably, while in 2006 Calderón had strong support in the lower chamber (41.2% of the Chamber of Deputies), in December 2009, following the midterm elections, his support had declined to a modest 28.4%.⁸² Thus, his appointments—which arguably might have been used to “control” the court—were of lesser importance, since he did not even have a majority to pass legislation. Calderón managed to propose and confirm Justices Zaldívar (2009), Aguilar (2009), Pardo (2011), Gutiérrez (2012), and Pérez (2012). Justices Gutiérrez and Pérez started their terms in December 2012, when Calderón was no longer President. So again, even though Calderón holds a rather impressive record of five appointments, only three justices served under his term. Timing-wise, none of these appointments strategically benefited his party.

President Peña's situation deviates slightly. Serving from December 1, 2012 to November 30, 2018, Peña's first Supreme Court appointment (Medina Mora) came at the beginning of 2015, three years after he took office. From the outset, Peña managed to achieve a near-absolute majority in Congress (42.8%);⁸³ and by 2015 he still enjoyed considerable support (40.4%). During his first three years, he exerted little or

⁸⁰ See recently Jaime Olaiz-González, *Mexican Supreme Court at Crossroads: Three Acts of Constitutional Politics*, 14 VIENNA J. ON INT'L CONST. L. 447 (2021) (analyzing the extraordinary tensions currently endured by the Supreme Court).

⁸¹ For a comparative analysis of the Mexican and American Supreme Court appointment processes, see Kevin Costello, *Supreme Court Politics and Life Tenure: A Comparative Inquiry*, 71 HASTINGS L.J. 29 (2020).

⁸² *Listado de Diputados por Grupo Parlamentario*, CÁMARA DE DIPUTADOS, https://sitlxi.diputados.gob.mx/listado_diputados_gnpn.php?tipot=TOTAL (last visited Apr. 27, 2022) (providing the composition of the Chamber of Deputies for the cited period).

⁸³ *Listado de Diputados por Grupo Parlamentario*, CÁMARA DE DIPUTADOS, https://sitlxi.diputados.gob.mx/listado_diputados_gnpn.php?tipot=TOTAL (last visited Apr. 27, 2022) (providing the composition of the Chamber of Deputies for the subsequent period).

no influence over the Court's composition, and his first appointment came only at the beginning of his third year. Furthermore, as his second and third appointments came at the end of his third year, it meant that of his six-year term, around 50% of the time he had no say in the Court's composition and only in the last third of his term did he influence the Court's composition in a meager percentage.

President López Obrador's situation stands out. His unexpected first and third appointments were anomalies. Not since the 1994 reforms has a president ever deferred a Supreme Court nomination to a successor or witnessed a Supreme Court justice's resignation. These unprecedented circumstances, rather than a supermajority flaw, propelled President López Obrador from a potentially disadvantageous position regarding nominations to an advantageous one concerning the timing of his selections.

A second factor challenging the court's control argument is the senatorial supermajority, stipulated in Article 96 of the Constitution. While the president plays an important role in the appointment process, without a senatorial supermajority this role remains restricted. A two-thirds supermajority in a 128-member Senate necessitates eighty-six votes. Unlike the Chamber of Deputies, the Senate does not face elections every three years, but enjoys a six-year term matching the president's term. Have Presidents Fox, Calderón, Peña, and López Obrador ever commanded such a senatorial supermajority to unreservedly appoint overtly loyal justices?

President Fox enjoyed 35.9% support in the Senate through the Partido Acción Nacional (PAN), with PRI representing 46.8%. President Calderón garnered slightly more support, securing 40.6% of the Senate, but fell significantly short of achieving the two-thirds senatorial supermajority. President Peña held the same majority as President Calderón (40.6%).

Before the advent of President López Obrador's era post-democratic transition, no president's party had even achieved an absolute majority in the Senate.⁸⁴ Thus, presidents had to rely on negotiation and pluralistic compromise⁸⁵ to ensure nominations.⁸⁶ President López was no exception, although he came close to the mark. MORENA's strong popular backing translated into sixty-one senators, or 47.6% of the Senate.⁸⁷ This is a modest increase compared to Presidents Calderón and Peña. Nevertheless, MORENA fell short of the supermajority required to appoint justices and relied on pluralistic agreements. There is decisive evidence to support this.

⁸⁴ While I recognize the existence of electoral coalitions, it is pertinent to highlight that they consist of distinct individual parties. Each party within a coalition mandates its own internal negotiations and political agreements. Thus, I do not view parties within a coalition as a single unified entity for the purposes of this analysis.

⁸⁵ Domingo anticipated that post the 1994 amendment, "appointments to the Supreme Court [would] inevitably involve inter-party negotiation." Domingo, *supra* note 23, at 714.

⁸⁶ The situation in Korea offers a contrasting perspective. There, short-term judicial appointments, combined with unwritten constitutional practices, arguably provide Korean presidents with greater discretion. PO JEN YAP & CHIEN-CHIH LIN, CONSTITUTIONAL CONVERGENCE IN EAST ASIA 41 (2021).

⁸⁷ *Integración de la LXV Legislatura*, SENADO DE LA REPÚBLICA, www.senado.gob.mx/65/senadores/integracion (last visited May 26, 2022).

The first justice appointed under MORENA was González Alcántara, who secured an astonishing 114 votes in his favor. Never in the modern era of the Supreme Court had a justice achieved this level of backing. Although the subsequent appointments of Justices Esquivel (with a 95-to-26 tally) and Ríos (94 to 28) faced some contention, they do not differ from the appointments of Silva Meza (89 to 24), Valls (85 to 29), Laynez (81 to 30), or Luna (95 to 26), not to mention the highly controversial appointment of Justice Medina Mora (achieving an opposition record of 83 to 35). President López Obrador's latest nomination, Justice Ortiz Ahlf, received an overwhelming 92-to-4 approval. This is an impressive feat: no justice has seen such low opposition since 1994. This presents a curious paradox. Despite Mexican politics being characterized by deep-seated polarization since 2018, half of President López Obrador's nominations have set consensus records in the Senate, highlighting the value of pluralistic participation.

3.3. Toward a stronger court's control argument?

My evaluation of the court's control argument, when applied to the Mexican supermajority, suggests that it is not conclusive from either a theoretical perspective or an analysis of constitutional politics. From a theoretical standpoint, I have demonstrated that this argument hinges on the assumption of significant problems with the appointment process. While procedural and judicial guarantees are far from perfect, they do provide a platform for pluralistic participation and preserve the independence of the justices. From a constitutional politics angle, I have shown that:

- (i) political parties have always required pluralistic consensus to appoint justices.
- (ii) MORENA is no outlier to this trend: it needed negotiation and political bargaining to reach the senatorial supermajority, in some instances even reaching extraordinary levels of consensus.
- (iii) Mexico's constitutional design prevents presidents from controlling the Court through staggered appointments.
- (iv) While President López Obrador has exerted greater influence on the court's composition due to early tenure appointments, this is an outcome of an unprecedented confluence of circumstances.

I recognize that there is room for a more nuanced argument. One could suggest that a supermajority might pave the way for court control through a combination of sincere voting and loyal justices. This perspective posits that it is unnecessary to "control" four justices; it is enough to control even one in complex cases to attain a significant impact. This argument would undoubtedly make some of the objections to the primary, "hard," argument moot, since a questionable appointment can pass more readily once than four times. The "hard" version of the argument hinges on substantial shortcomings, while its subtler variant does not. However, even as a beefed-up proposition, it still relies on an extrinsic factor, namely the potential to exceptionally appoint one or two ultra-loyal justices without pluralistic senatorial oversight.

Another perspective posits that the subtler court's control argument is relevant only in complex scenarios. It is predicated on several independent justices agreeing on the constitutionality of a statute based on sincere reasons and valid constitutional theories. Here, the crux is if a political majority has an iron grip on a single justice, it may end up controlling the court in all cases in which a 7-to-3 decision is prevalent, making the "controlled" justice the arbiter. However, given that several justices must sincerely back a statute for such a scenario to materialize, the number of such occurrences is severely limited.

This variant of the court's control argument implies that having one "controlled justice" can occasionally favor legislation. However, bare majority systems are not immune to this problem, albeit in another context. In a bare majority system, influencing a single judge could toggle the decision to uphold or strike down a law. The United States is proof of this, where, historically, a single vote stood between upholding or overturning *Roe v. Wade*. Even though deferential supermajority systems might inherently favor the constitutionality of a statute,⁸⁸ this does not negate the fact that the same argument holds water for bare majority systems too. The difference is quantitative (the percentage of influence it would have on the case), not qualitative. If the subtler version of the court's control argument depends on showing that a voting system ought to be sidelined because it offers "controlled justices," who are appointed by methods designed to ensure their autonomy, a marginally more amplified influence than in bare majorities, then the supermajority may withstand the scrutiny.

4. The paralysis argument

4.1. Do supermajorities paralyze the court? An introduction to a verifiable objection

One of the most frequently cited arguments against supermajorities is their potential to paralyze the court, inhibiting it from striking down legislation.⁸⁹ The Venice Commission, a globally esteemed international body, has declared that a supermajority "carries the risk of blocking the decision-making process of the Tribunal and of rendering the Constitutional Tribunal ineffective, making it impossible for the Tribunal to carry out its key task of ensuring the constitutionality of legislation."⁹⁰ Even scholars who endorse supermajorities have recognized that this is one of the most important arguments to consider against supermajorities.⁹¹

⁸⁸ It should be emphasized that within deferential supermajorities there is a transfer of decisional power from the majority to the minority. The minority wields greater influence due to its capacity to block a declaration of unconstitutionality, thereby assuming a decision-making role previously held by the majority.

⁸⁹ Zellmer & Miller, *supra* note 58, at 87.

⁹⁰ Venice Commission, Opinion No. 833/2015 on Amendments to the Act of 25 June 2015 on the Constitutional Tribunal. CDL-AD(2016)001, at 25 (Mar. 11, 2016).

⁹¹ Shugerman, *supra* note 9, at 985; Entin, *supra* note 41, at 466; Roznai, *supra* note 14, at 371; Castillo-Ortiz, *supra* note 13, at 640.

The court paralysis argument can be interpreted in two ways. First, it can be viewed as a philosophical objection to the very concept of supermajority whenever it impedes striking down a statute. Seen this way, the argument is a theoretical critique of supermajorities as such, regardless of their operational efficiency. Alternatively, the argument suggests that supermajorities place undue burden, and that, *in practice*, they take a significant toll on the court's ability to reach the needed consensus. The former is a theoretical perspective, while the latter can be empirically verified. I will explore the empirical angle.⁹²

It is somewhat surprising that this argument often lacks empirical evidence to support the purported paralysis, considering the existence of multiple enduring supermajorities in comparative law.⁹³ Presently, quantitative empirical evidence is available only from Peru⁹⁴ and South Korea.⁹⁵ Earlier studies in the United States predominantly focused on qualitative analysis.⁹⁶

However, some existing data suggests that, contrary to popular belief, supermajorities do not necessarily paralyze the court. In fact, in some countries, they rarely affect the outcome of cases. It is reasonable to assume that courts will generally reach agreement. Even in systems operating under a bare majority rule, many decisions will emerge from a supermajority. Supermajorities come into play in cases marked by intense disagreement, where both stances have valid constitutional rationale. That is precisely the purpose. Deferential supermajorities do not try to hinder the court from striking down legislation, but rather grant minimal deference to particularly disputed cases. In the next section, I will examine this hypothesis in the context of Mexico.

4.2. The paralysis argument in Mexico: An empirical refutation

To evaluate the paralysis argument within the Mexican context, I turned to empirical data. I scrutinized decisions from the Supreme Court, available in the Court's database from January 1, 1995 to April 27, 2022,⁹⁷ focusing on abstract normative review (actions of unconstitutionality and general declarations of unconstitutionality)

⁹² On the first version of the argument, see Waldron, *supra* note 10; Caviedes, *supra* note 15.

⁹³ Riley, *supra* note 3, at 21, 633 (analyzing several rulings where the supermajority determined the case's outcome, yet overlooking the fact that the proportion did not block the court. Riley cites three cases as proof that a prevailing supermajority inherently signaled an untenable situation).

⁹⁴ Dargent, *supra* note 7. See also LYDIA BRASHEAR TIEDE, JUDICIAL VETOS: DECISION-MAKING ON MIXED SELECTION CONSTITUTIONAL COURTS (2022) (examining the decision-making process of the Chilean Constitutional Court, which operates under a supermajority, though not focusing on supermajority rules).

⁹⁵ Hong, *supra* note 6.

⁹⁶ See Madgett, *supra* note 1, at 338; Entin, *supra* note 41, at 468 (acknowledging, despite his criticism of the supermajority, that it took half a century for the supermajority to determine the outcome of a case); Shugerman, *supra* note 9, at 956 n.376 (offering a list of cases where the supermajority was applied in Ohio from 1912 up to 1968).

⁹⁷ The dataset is limited to published decisions due to the Mexican Court's practice of *engrose*, where a case is publicly deliberated and decided, but its official publication (dated retroactively) may be delayed for months or even years. See the [online Appendix](#).

where the supermajority is pertinent.⁹⁸ I pinpointed decisions where the supermajority prevented striking down a provision, terming these “supermajority failure decisions.” Out of these, a subset of 137 supermajority failure decisions was examined to determine the number of provisions challenged in each individual case (the number varied from one to fifty, and more). Outcomes of each provision were then recorded manually.⁹⁹

What do the data reveal? Brage’s 2005 analysis had a profound influence on the Mexican debate. By the time Brage presented his findings, the supermajority had been functioning for nearly a decade. However, his criticism was purely theoretical, devoid of empirical insights. As of early 2004, the Supreme Court had failed to achieve a supermajority only eight times.

Most of the early decisions in which the supermajority played a role were neither political nor controversial.¹⁰⁰ An exception was AI 10/2000, in which the Court failed to achieve a supermajority to repeal legislation permitting the public prosecutor to authorize abortions in cases of rape. Interestingly, in this early high-profile case, the supermajority leaned toward upholding rights.¹⁰¹ Had Brage looked at the effective functioning of the supermajority, he might have conceded that, while he disapproved of it theoretically, in practical terms the supermajority did not obstruct the court. What has happened since then?

From its inception (January 1, 1995) to April 27, 2022, the supermajority defended a legal provision in 137 cases, influencing 10.1% of the cases reviewed by the Supreme Court in abstract terms. In the remaining 89.9% of the cases, *ceteris paribus*, the Court’s decision would most likely have been the same with or without the

⁹⁸ I will focus the analysis on actions of unconstitutionality and general declarations of unconstitutionality, due to their consistent applicability of supermajority and potential for *erga omnes* effects; whereas in constitutional controversies (concrete review), public bodies seldom challenge statutes, and even if they do, they follow a distinct regime pertaining to effects.

⁹⁹ The dataset identifies four possible categories of outcome: (i) provisions upheld; (ii) provisions declared unconstitutional; (iii) provisions dismissed on formal grounds; and (iv) provisions where the supermajority effectively barred the statute’s nullification. I assigned a numerical value of “1” to each category. In cases where a single article had several outcomes (partially struck down, partially upheld, partially dismissed on formal grounds), I divided the value (1) among the outcomes, using fractions like 0.25, 0.33, or 0.50. Possibilities of manual coding errors should be acknowledged. Detailed methodological specifications and the dataset are available as an [online Appendix](#).

¹⁰⁰ For examples of such decisions, see *Acción de inconstitucionalidad 12/2002*, Pleno de la Suprema Corte de Justicia de la Nación [SCJN] [Supreme Court], Oct. 22, 2002 (Mex.) (concerning a regulation forcing banks to implement security protocols, such as bank security cameras); *Acción de inconstitucionalidad 13/2002*, Pleno de la Suprema Corte de Justicia de la Nación [SCJN] [Supreme Court], Nov. 11, 2003 (Mex.) (concerning the labor regime applicable to employees of a state’s Human Rights Commission).

¹⁰¹ See, e.g., Zellmer & Miller, *supra* note 58, at 85 (voicing the popular argument that supermajorities block the ability of the court to protect vulnerable individuals and minorities. That is not always the case: the doctrine often assumes that all judicial review is liberal and protective while legislation is intrusive and abusive). On the significance of the supermajority toward pro-abortion legislation, see 1 STEVEN G. CALABRESI, *THE HISTORY AND GROWTH OF JUDICIAL REVIEW: THE G-20 COMMON LAW COUNTRIES AND ISRAEL* (2021) (asserting that due to the supermajority, “the entire abortion reform law was upheld and remained on the books.” *Id.* at 239. However, the law was not upheld, as the challenge was dismissed. Calabresi misses the crucial difference, mentioned earlier, between upholding and dismissal (*desestimación*)).

supermajority requirement if Justices had voted in a similar fashion. Figure 1 shows the evolution of Mexican supermajority failure decisions over the years.

A preliminary takeaway, resonating with Hong’s examination of the South Korean supermajority, might be that the rule does not significantly paralyze the Court.¹⁰²

However, the data presented above might not accurately represent the supermajority’s role. In the American system of judicial review, one could plausibly argue that a supermajority would often lead to full case resolution or at least significantly influence it. The American model only considers a statute’s unconstitutionality when required to settle a specific case. In contrast, the Mexican action of unconstitutionality is rooted in the Kelsenian system. Within the Kelsenian abstract review framework, the fact that the supermajority was not achieved does not mean that the entire case was “resolved” because of the supermajority; rather, it means the supermajority was decisive in one of the challenges brought by the plaintiff. The same plea may have challenged multiple legal provisions, sometimes on disparate and even unrelated grounds. Since plaintiffs in Kelsenian systems often are not required to prove legal interest, they could contest several provisions within a single plea, a scenario likely more complicated in the American model. The constitutionality of each challenged article is typically voted upon individually in the Kelsenian system, meaning a supermajority failure in one article does not affect the others.

Cases in which a supermajority failure decisively resolved an entire case are rare in the history of the Mexican Supreme Court. Of the 1357 rulings issued during the studied period, the supermajority “decided the case” entirely in only eighteen cases: a mere 1.32% of the time. In the remaining 98.68% of the cases, failing to achieve a

Figure 1. Supermajority failure decisions in the Mexican Supreme Court (1995–2022)

¹⁰² During the period of 2003–16, Hong identified an average of 3.2 failed supermajority decisions per year in Korea. Hong, *supra* note 6, at 194.

supermajority on one article did not prevent the Court from addressing other constitutional challenges.

To elucidate, consider AI 69/2019, where plaintiffs contested several articles of the Administrative Responsibility Act of the State of Nuevo León.¹⁰³ These challenges were often unrelated, with the plaintiffs arguing that the provisions infringed the principles of privacy, legality, federalism, equality, autonomy, or human rights. The Court reviewed fifty-seven articles in this ruling. Out of these, more than thirteen articles were upheld and more than forty-two were struck down. The supermajority was influential in upholding only half of an article (to be precise, one paragraph, whereas the rest of the article was declared unconstitutional). So, to claim that AI 69/2019 was “decided” by the supermajority rule would be a gross exaggeration.

Conversely, there are rulings in which the supermajority had more influence than a “simpler” dataset might show. In AI 47/2019, for example, the Court was presented with a challenge, by the President of the Republic and the National Human Rights Commission, against almost eighty legal provisions of the Income Act of the Municipality of Atlatlahuacan in Morelos.¹⁰⁴ Here, the supermajority’s role was more prominent than in AI 69/2019, emphasizing that simple datasets might not capture the nuance of the supermajority’s influence. For a thorough assessment of the supermajority’s impact within the Mexican system, a deeper analysis is necessary.

In the set of 137 decisions where the supermajority failed, 323.31 provisions remained intact due to the supermajority’s influence. However, in the same rulings, 950.98 provisions were upheld, 149.82 provisions were sidelined without a formal analysis,¹⁰⁵ and 773.64 were struck down. Thus, even within those decisions influenced by the supermajority, only 14.7% of the provisions were protected by the rule. Taking into account that these decisions make up only 10.1% of the Supreme Court’s abstract review decisions from the period, the real impact of the supermajority stands at approximately 1.48% of all such cases reviewed by the Supreme Court.

The numbers associated with the supermajority might be somewhat inflated due to specific circumstances. For example, in 2014, the Court encountered multiple challenges regarding the competency of local congresses to regulate electoral coalitions. Unable to achieve a supermajority agreement, the Court repeatedly issued supermajority failure decisions on several identical state statutes.¹⁰⁶ The same discussion and voting were repeated in AI 41/2017 and 142/2017.¹⁰⁷ Almost 10%

¹⁰³ Acción de inconstitucionalidad 69/2019, Pleno de la Suprema Corte de Justicia de la Nación [SCJN] [Supreme Court], Mar. 01, 2021 (Mex.).

¹⁰⁴ Acción de inconstitucionalidad 47/2019, Pleno de la Suprema Corte de Justicia de la Nación [SCJN] [Supreme Court], Oct. 24, 2019 (Mex.).

¹⁰⁵ Formal reasons include: (i) the plaintiff’s lack of legal standing; (ii) the statute’s repeal by the Congress; and (iii) the challenge being presented beyond the stipulated time limits. For a more detailed explanation, see the [online Appendix](#).

¹⁰⁶ Acción de inconstitucionalidad 32/2014, Pleno de la Suprema Corte de Justicia de la Nación [SCJN] [Supreme Court], Sept. 22, 2014 (Mex.). The subsequent nine decisions, as shown in the [online Appendix](#), are instances of supermajority failures on identical electoral statutes.

¹⁰⁷ Acción de inconstitucionalidad 41/2017, Pleno de la Suprema Corte de Justicia de la Nación [SCJN] [Supreme Court], Aug. 24, 2017 (Mex.); Acción de inconstitucionalidad 142/2017, Pleno de la Suprema Corte de Justicia de la Nación [SCJN] [Supreme Court], Dec. 05, 2017 (Mex.).

of supermajority dismissals revolved around similar topics, essentially echoing a split court's voting on a particular issue. This suggests that the supermajority may have less impact on the Court's functioning if we take into account the constitutional questions addressed by the Court, rather than the rulings in which the same questions have been repeated.

If we take into account only cases in which the supermajority had any impact, the Court, on average, upheld 43.22% of the articles and invalidated 35.2% of the challenged provisions. Determining whether this rate of unconstitutionality is typical or how it compares internationally is not easy. As Tiede and Ponce have pointed out, unconstitutionality rates are hardly comparable across jurisdictions, given the variations in the scope of judicial review and institutional design.¹⁰⁸ For context, Tiede recently cited a 24% unconstitutionality rate for Colombia (not functioning with a supermajority) and,¹⁰⁹ jointly with Ponce, posited that Peru (functioning under a supermajority) had a 33% unconstitutionality rate.¹¹⁰

Mexico's unconstitutionality rate in supermajority failure decisions might be even higher. Tiede and Ponce calculate the unconstitutionality rate "by dividing the number of cases in which a law or order was found unconstitutional by the total number of cases in which the constitutionality of a law was at issue."¹¹¹ Using this method for Mexico, of the 137 rulings in the dataset, ninety-one cases declared at least one legal provision unconstitutional, resulting in a 66.4% rate of unconstitutionality.

To summarize, the supermajority decisively affected only eighteen cases. In the remaining cases, the supermajority might have prevented the invalidation of a single provision, but consensus was reached on upholding or striking down other contested provisions. Even considering only the 137 supermajority-influenced cases, only 14.7% of the challenged statutes were saved.

It could be objected that this quantitative approach fails to consider a qualitative aspect of the case. Suppose a supermajority is most likely to arise in contested and controversial cases. In that case, it might be that the supermajority would still have a substantial qualitative impact on the case, protecting the most critical articles.¹¹² To test this hypothesis, I further classified every single decision within the dataset. I performed a qualitative analysis of the provisions protected by the supermajority

¹⁰⁸ Lydia Brashear Tiede & Aldo Fernando Ponce, *Evaluating Theories of Decision-Making on the Peruvian Constitutional Tribunal*, 6 J. POL. LATIN AM. 139, 156 (2014). See also Oliver W. Lembcke, *The German Federal Constitutional Court: Authority Transformed into Power?*, in CONSTITUTIONAL POLITICS AND THE JUDICIARY 32, 69 (Kálmán Pócsa ed., 2018) (citing a 43% unconstitutionality rate for the German Constitutional Court up to 2015). The article excludes from the count those decisions in which the Court refused to resolve the merits for formal reasons. The data cover both concrete and abstract review cases. The basis for comparison is thus strictly delimited.

¹⁰⁹ TIEDE, *supra* note 95, at 216.

¹¹⁰ Tiede & Ponce, *supra* note 109, at 156. The Peruvian and Colombian examples are comparable to the Mexican one. In both rates, only abstract review was considered and the methodology to gather data is comparable. Also, the cases pertain to mandatory jurisdiction where certiorari may not play a role.

¹¹¹ *Id.*

¹¹² I thank an anonymous reviewer for this important remark.

ranking the rule's impact as decisive, very relevant, moderate, and low.¹¹³ Of the 137 decisions, the influence of the supermajority was very relevant in 32.8% of the cases (forty-five). In 26.2% (thirty-six) the impact was low, in 23.3% (thirty-two) decisive, and in 17.5% moderate (twenty-four). Therefore, the rule significantly impacted a case in 56% of the rulings, which is still less than 6% of the court's decisions in the dataset (1357).

4.3. Paralysis argument and presidential peak of influence

The president's ability to influence the Supreme Court's composition is often believed to enhance her or his power to paralyze the Court through the supermajority. By nominating Court members, the president is presumed to position allies on the Court. While these allies may not be directly "controlled," they might exhibit greater deference to the president's policies. To evaluate this claim, we must identify any correlation between presidential influence and the frequency of supermajority failures. I call the "peak of presidential influence" the moment when a president has the greatest number of his or her nominees on the court, maximizing his or her influence over the Court's makeup. Does the frequency of supermajority failures shift during the peak of presidential influence?

The data suggest it does not. [Figure 2](#) compares the key moments of peak presidential influence. Both Presidents Fox and Calderón reached their peak of influence in their final year, when most of their proposed justices were active on the Court.

Figure 2. Presidential peaks of influence vs. supermajority failures (2000–22)

¹¹³ If the core contention of the plea (or the main claim) was blocked by the supermajority, I labeled its influence as "decisive." If the article(s) protected were significant, but were accompanied by other relevant issues that were discussed and voted upon, I categorized them as "very relevant." The "very relevant" category indicates that while the preserved article was a central point of the plea, the plaintiff presented multiple substantial challenges. Articles that carry weight, but are not the plea's central focus, are categorized as "moderate." Meanwhile, when an article is evidently challenged in connection to more substantial constitutional issues and has no real importance within the plea, I classified the supermajority's influence as "low."

President Peña enjoyed a somewhat longer period of influence (2016–18); this study thus used an average for the full period. Even though 2022 data for President López Obrador is not yet available,¹¹⁴ the year 2021 has been used for reference, as he had proposed and confirmed three justices by that year, which is already on par with other presidents. Figure 3 juxtaposes this with the peak supermajority failure years for each presidential term, showing no apparent correlation.¹¹⁵

Aside from the example of President López Obrador, in every other case the supermajority failure peak is at least two years apart from the presidential peak of influence over the Court's composition¹¹⁶ (or even three years, as in the cases of Presidents Fox and Calderón).¹¹⁷

4.4. Why isn't the Mexican Supreme Court paralyzed? Hypotheses and constraints

Why would a court under a supermajority seem to operate similarly to other constitutional courts without this requirement? Two factors likely combine. First, courts

Figure 3. Peak years of supermajority failures per presidential period (2000–22)

¹¹⁴ Justice Ortiz Ahlf, President López Obrador's most recent nominee, commenced his tenure on the Court on December 12, 2021. Hence, from January 2022 onwards, the Supreme Court has operated with four justices nominated by López Obrador, namely Justices González Alcántara, Ríos, Esquivel, and Ortiz Ahlf.

¹¹⁵ Figures 2 and 3 depict in dark gray the total number of supermajority failure decisions (i.e., a decision in which the supermajority prevented a statute from being struck down). In light gray they show the exact number of statutes / legal provisions preserved by the failure to achieve a supermajority, thereby showing the precise impact of those supermajority failures.

¹¹⁶ The lack of relationship between the president's peak year of influence and the years in which supermajority failure decisions are most frequent in each presidential term is significant. Even if we take into account that actions of unconstitutionality are resolved on average in slightly more than one year, the peaks still do not match this period.

¹¹⁷ As both Presidents Fox and Calderón are affiliated with PAN, this complicates the analysis pertaining to Calderón, especially since he "inherited" the justices nominated by Fox. It is plausible that both sought to nominate Justices who would be more sympathetic to their party's positions. However, the tenures of Presidents Fox, Peña, and López Obrador provide instances where presidents engage with courts the composition of which eluded their respective parties' influence.

tend to organically build consensus, whether it is to strike down or uphold legislation. Second, judges in supermajority systems might exhibit less deference to legislation than those in simple majority systems. Nonetheless, the supermajority ensures a degree of deference through aggregate voting.

However, the dataset reveals some intriguing patterns. Since 2014, the Court has substantially increased the number of failed supermajority decisions. It could be argued that the Court is becoming less dialogical, leading to a more pronounced role for the supermajority due to increasing dissensus and an apparent reluctance among justices to seek the middle ground. Future studies should address these issues. While some researchers have pointed out the impact of several factors, such as less dialogical Justices, others claim that the introduction in 2006 of public deliberations transmitted on television could have negatively impacted the court's consensus capability,¹¹⁸ although without providing empirical evidence for the claim in terms of correlation or causality.

From an empirical standpoint, I feel I have addressed the paralysis argument. I presume critics of the supermajority will resort to the first variation of this argument: i.e., the philosophical objection, or a qualitative argument. Critics might claim that even if the supermajority lacks a significant impact from a statistical point of view, it affects the court from a qualitative perspective. On such a view, the cases in which the supermajority decides the outcome would be deemed as paralysis in a broader perspective.

Detractors could suggest that cases like the Federal Remuneration Act case¹¹⁹ are crucial to the Court's functioning, and that no matter how infrequent, these cases prove the need to abandon the supermajority. The premises of this argument, however, already contain its conclusion: it presumes that simple majorities always arrive at the "correct" outcome and the supermajority is wrong because it preserves statutes that ought to have been invalidated. Engaging with a qualitative version of this argument inevitably leads the debate evaluating the supposed correct outcome in specific cases. Caviedes labels these cases "false negatives," noting the difficulty in reaching consensus on which statutes should to have been declared unconstitutional and which were rightfully protected by the supermajority.¹²⁰

¹¹⁸ Francisca Pou Giménez, *Changing the Channel: Broadcasting Deliberations in the Mexican Supreme Court*, in *JUSTICES AND JOURNALISTS* 209 (Richard Davis & David Taras eds., 2017); SAÚL LÓPEZ, *LA SUPREMA CORTE Y SU PROCESO DE DECISIÓN: NI TRANSPARENCIA NI CALIDAD DELIBERATIVA* 58–60 (2019).

¹¹⁹ *Acción de inconstitucionalidad 105/2018 y su acumulada 108/2018*, Pleno de la Suprema Corte de Justicia de la Nación [SCJN] [Supreme Court], May 20, 2019 (Mex.).

¹²⁰ Caviedes, *supra* note 15 (pointing out that, even if there is consensus on the constitutionality of specific statutes, independent of the Court's decision, it is essential that we recognize that the Court can make mistakes. These errors might manifest in either striking down constitutional legislation or preserving unconstitutional legislation. Such mistakes are a natural part of the judicial process. Opponents of the supermajority cannot claim that all cases settled by a simple majority are unquestionably unconstitutional; some might be mistakes. The debate surrounding abortion in cases of rape is a prime example where much of the Mexican legal scholarship would agree on its constitutionality, yet it might have been overturned by a simple majority. Thus, it is evident that while a supermajority can lead to "false negatives," simple majorities also produce "false positives." See Caviedes, *supra* note 15, at 1183–5). The question is, how many of them? Moreover, who gets to decide which one is a false positive or a false negative, and how?

Lastly, it is crucial to acknowledge the limitations of this section. First, comparing unconstitutionality rates is inherently challenging. Even with some context data provided, determining a court's degree of deference depends on multiple factors, such as legal standing, constitutional culture, and political environment. Second, scholars may genuinely disagree in their qualitative assessments of the impact of the supermajority rule in particular cases. Additionally, regarding the peak of presidential influence, the present analysis only examines the variation of supermajority failure decisions in relation to the sitting president and her or his sway over the court's composition; it does not delve into other presidential avenues of influence or potential court deference to presidential policy.

5. Conclusions

This article has sought to enrich a global discussion on supermajorities in constitutional adjudication by addressing two common theoretical objections through an in-depth look at the Mexican context. My findings indicate that well-balanced appointments, combined with other measures that promote judicial independence, can counteract the common objection about potential control of the court. Specifically, in the Mexican system, the staggered appointment of Justices and pluralistic senatorial supermajorities act as strong systemic safeguards.

Regarding the paralysis argument, the empirical analysis demonstrates that this objection does not hold substantial weight in the Mexican context. This is in line with findings from other systems with supermajorities, such as South Korea¹²¹ and Peru.¹²² Current empirical studies appear to favor supermajorities as functional models.

This article also highlights some challenges within the Mexican supermajority model. However, recognizing problems within supermajorities does not necessarily invalidate their worth as valid models. Simple majority systems, too, come with their set of shortcomings, yet judicial review has not abandoned them. I acknowledge that endorsing the supermajority as a functional model in the Mexican case is open to scrutiny. Nevertheless, I do contend that a persuasive case has been made in refuting two prominent objections against supermajorities. This exploration of the supermajority dynamic in Mexico further bridges theoretical debate and empirical research.

¹²¹ Hong, *supra* note 6.

¹²² Dargent, *supra* note 7.